

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: GANA

FIRST NAME: AHMED

PROGRAM CODE: PHGH

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: RP6

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 4%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What are the processes involved in research?

- Research Question, Hypothesis, Methods, and Discussion
- Research Proposal, Appropriate Methodology and Discussion
- Introduction, Literature Review, Methodology and Discussion
- A systematic process of inquiry involving Conceptualization, Proposal, Literature Review, Data Generation and Analysis, Inference, and reporting to the public¹**

2. Concerning Plagiarism, which of the statements below is correct?

- Less than 25% for a good reason without citation is acceptable

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertation: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninthth edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 19-20.

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- Plagiarism is entirely unacceptable in academic writing
- Plagiarism up to 25% for a good reason and accompanied by a citation²**
- As low as 14% is considered acceptable even without appropriate citation and referencing

3. **How can a researcher succinctly summarize his research work to attract readership?**

- An Executive Summary of 5-10 pages containing aspects of the entire research work in multiple paragraphs
- A summary report of the research with references and page numbers
- An abstract: a concise, self-contained summary of the research paper without references to actual paper or outside sources and highlights key content areas, research purpose, importance of work, and primary outcomes³**
- A detailed abstract with multiple paragraphs, pages, and references

4. **What is an effective literature review?**

- A summary review of similar articles from previous Ph.D. dissertations only
- A written overview of major writings and other sources on a selected topic, including scholarly journal articles, books, government reports, and websites. The literature review provides**

² EUCLID, *EUCLID Student's Orientation Manual*, (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2021), page no.

³ Kate L. Turabian, 1,110-1,150,

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a description, summary, and critical review/evaluation of each source⁴

- A summarized or paraphrased review of all relevant previous studies on the topic under the introduction chapter of the research
- A critical review of articles is unnecessary when doing a literature review once previous articles and research have been mentioned

5. Which of the following statements aptly describes research methods and methodology?

- Research methods and methodologies have the same meaning and purpose in research and can be used interchangeably
- Qualitative and Quantitative techniques are the only accepted methods for research, and the mixed-research method is not recognized scientifically
- A detailed description of methods is not an essential component of dissertation research
- Research methods are the strategies, processes, or techniques utilized in the collection of data or evidence for analysis, while research methodologies are the primary principles that will guide the research⁵**

6. The best way to present the infographics of research findings is by using

- Tables, charts, infographics, text

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, 70-80.

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, **Fourth** ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 80–85.

Tables, graphs, charts, plots⁶

Tables, figures, data, graphs

Tables, figures, data, text

7. How can a researcher provide a clear and logical interpretation of the results of his research, linking the research proposal, questions, and findings in a way that stresses the significance of the study?

Conclusion: A summary of the point is not intended to help the reader understand why your research should matter to them after they have finished reading the paper

A conclusion: a summary of the points or a re-statement of your research problem, as well as the synthesis of key points in a logical manner aimed at justifying the significance of the research and its findings⁷

Conclusion: a mere summary of points from research done without necessarily synthesizing them

The conclusion is part of the research paper that brings everything together in a generic manner, introduces new issues, and apologizes for the researcher's shortcomings

8. In the Turabian Citation style, the Footnotes of a single Author is written as follows under the Notes section:

Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. *Title of Book: Subtitle of Book*. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, 80–100.

⁷ Linda D. Bloomberg, 87-89.

Author's First and last Names, *Title of the Book: Subtitle of Book* (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication), Page Number⁸

Author's First and Last Names, Title of the Book: Subtitle of Book. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication, Page Number

Author's Last and First Names, *Title of the Book: Subtitle of the Book* (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication), Page Number

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1. 9. Dates are formatted using the WHO style guide as follows

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Month-Day-Year

10. How should numbers be written when they are part of the text (not as a citation)?

All numbers are written in figures

All numbers are spelled out unless used in a specific numerical context or a series of numbers

Numbers are written in either numbers or figures depending on what audience one writes for (e.g., numbers in scientific research papers are always written in figures)

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⁸ Kate L. Turabian, 148-149.

⁹ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 52.

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- Numbers less than ten are spelled out. Numbers 10 and higher are written in figures unless used in a specific numerical context or a series of numbers¹⁰**

¹⁰ World Health Organization, 52.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. **Fourth** ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph Bizup, Williams Fitzgerald, and University of Chicago Press Staff. **Ninth** ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

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World Health Organization. *WHO **Style Guide***. Geneva: World Health Organization Press, 2013.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.